

Benchmarking a BEM numerical model for a floating wind platform dynamics in Chilean offshore conditions

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ABSTRACT: Given the local conditions and capabilities, semi-submersible floating offshore wind turbines (FOWT) appear to be the most suitable concept for harnessing Chile's substantial offshore wind energy potential. However, compared to Spar or Tension Leg Platforms (TLP) like the proposed in the INF4INITY project, semi-submersibles tend to experience greater motions. Since large motions and accelerations are critical to the survivability of these platforms, it is essential to quantify them during the design process. Consequently, efficient modelling becomes a desired feature on the initial phase of the design, such that it allows to optimize the platform following an iterative process. This study evaluates the accuracy and applicability of a numerical model formulated in the frequency domain and based on the Boundary Element Method (BEM). The behavior of a generic semi-submersible wind energy platform under both operational and extreme conditions is assessed, with results compared to experimental data. Analyses include platform motion and mooring forces in both regular and irregular wave conditions. The obtained results reveal the limitations of the numerical model when applying to model the behaviour of FOWT, and methods for improvement are suggested for future investigations.

1 INTRODUCTION

Interest in offshore wind energy has grown significantly in recent years as a means to reduce greenhouse gas emissions (Sherman et al. 2020, Browning & Lenox 2020, Li et al. 2022). This energy source benefits from the expertise developed by the offshore oil and gas industry as well as the onshore wind sector (Hewitt 2003). Additionally, offshore wind energy offers several advantages over onshore wind: it harnesses stronger and more consistent winds (Bilgili et al. 2011), and it mitigates visual and noise impacts on the population (Kaldellis et al. 2016, Lee et al. 2020). Although promising projections indicate a decline in energy costs in the coming years (DNV GL 2020, Wiser et al. 2016, Wiser et al. 2021), considerable efforts are still required to achieve competitive costs compared to conventional energy sources.

Modeling the dynamics of Floating Offshore Wind Turbines (FOWTs) is a critical step in their design process, as it allows for the prediction of their responses under various environmental conditions. Wave and mooring loads are the most relevant for assessing critical aspects of their design. Thus, as-

sessing the dynamics under these loads becomes crucial on the initial stage of the design. Also, mean drift forces estimation is essential for mooring system design. Numerical models are commonly employed due to their lower costs compared to physical models. Among numerical models, the Boundary Element Method (BEM) solvers are frequently used during this initial design stage because they are more cost-effective than Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) models, though with some compromise on accuracy (Otter et al. 2022). Thus, this method allows to estimate motions and mean drift forces efficiently.

This study evaluates the accuracy of a frequency domain numerical model based on BEM theory and potential flow theory to simulate the dynamic of FOWT under waves and mooring loads. Using a free source BEM solver, radiation and wave excitation forces are computed. Then, an approximation of viscous and mooring loads is incorporated by doing a linearization of them based on the results of free decay tests. To this end, a comparison of the dynamics of a generic platform under operational and extreme sea states is made between numerical and experimental results. Besides, numerical simulation of mean drift

forces by applying far-field method is assessed.

2 PHYSICAL MODEL

2.1 Generic platform

The experiments were carried out using a generic FOWT model designed and built in (Hertzsch 2020). The platform was designed considering Chilean local conditions and using the 5 [MW] offshore wind turbine developed by the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) as a reference turbine, (Jonkman, Butterfield, Musial, & Scott 2009). In order to define the platform main dimensions, a database of existing semi-submersible FOWT was made and an axisymmetric shape with three columns was chosen, Figure 1. To define the final dimensions, a Sobol algorithm was used to evaluate multiple combinations of geometry and mass properties based on four selection criteria: initial stability to obtaining a maximum pitch angle of $\theta_{max} = 8^\circ$, platform mass to reduce production costs, feasibility to fabricate the model, and sensitivity to changes in mass and center of gravity wave tank tests. Lastly, considering the tank characteristics and construction capabilities, a strategic 87.2 scale factor was selected to fabricate the model, Figure 1, resulting in the final dimensions and mass properties of the platform, (see Table 1).

Figure 1: Generic floating wind platform geometry, source: (Hertzsch 2020).

Table 1: Platform main dimensions and mass properties.

Characteristic	Full scale	Model scale
Displacement (Δ) [kg]	15630	23.573
Length (L_p) [m]	54.9	0.630
Beam (B) [m]	63.4	0.727
Draft (h) [m]	26.9	0.309
Columns diameter (d_p) [m]	15.7	0.18
KG [m]	29	0.333
Radio of gyration [m]	29	0.333

2.2 Experimental setup

During these experiments only wave and mooring loads were considered. The experimental tests were performed in the Wave and Towing Tank at Universidad Austral de Chile, which is 40 m long and has a 3 m wide and 2 m high transverse section. In this experiments 1.75 m water depth (h) was used. At one end of the tank a wave generator which is able to operate

Figure 2: Experimental setup and coordinate system definition (measurements in m).

in flap and piston modes and generate regular and irregular waves is installed, while a passive absorption system is installed in the opposite end.

The platform was modelled as a rigid body such that the mass properties of the model correspond to the whole structure. The model was deployed 9.12 m far away from the generator paddle. A three-line-horizontal mooring system at the height of the water level was employed, resulting in a symmetric XZ plane system (see Figure 2). The mooring lines were composed of a steel cable with 1.6 mm diameter and a spring of restoring constant equal to 125.1 N/m. The spring was located at the fix end point of each mooring line. Tension forces in the three mooring lines were recorded by S-type load cells located between the fix point of the mooring line and the spring. Four wave gauges were installed in the vicinity of the model; one of them located upstream (WG2), one on the side of the model (WG1) and two downstream (WG3 and WG4). The motions of the platform were measured by a Qualisys motion capture system composed by four M1 cameras. Since the waves were one-direction, only surge, heave and pitch motions were assessed.

2.3 Wave conditions

In order to obtain the Response Amplitude Operators (RAO) of the platform, 16 regular waves were generated, corresponding to wave lengths (λ) from 1.5 to 6 times the platform length (L_p) and angular frequencies (ω) from 4.04 rad/s to 8.08 rad/s in model scale. To avoid non linear effects in these tests, wave height was defined aiming to achieve a wave steepness close to 3.5%, giving a range from 0.031 m to 0.128 mm (see Figure 3). Most of these waves are in deep waters regime. These waves were previously generated and measured without the model.

Three sea states were evaluated for a potential deployment site in southern Chile, assessed in (Lucero et al. 2017), (see Table 2). The operational sea state corresponds to the most frequent wave condition on the reference site. Annual storm sea state was selected as a hard but still frequent wave condition, being representative of a typical annual storm. Finally the 100 years storm sea state is equivalent to a 100 years re-

Figure 3: Wave theory regime of the assessed regular and irregular waves (in logarithmic scale).

turn period condition, being the most extreme condition assessed. These selected conditions characterized in terms of significant height and peak period were simulated in the wave tank considering a JONSWAP spectral distribution and a duration equivalent to 3 hours in full scale, obtaining a good agreement (see Figure 4). Although a slight difference was obtained in the operational and annual storm wave spectrum, it is due to the definition of a maximum frequency limit of the wave generator. While some of these sea states correspond to extreme conditions, all of them can be modelled applying linear theory (see Figure 3). The operational and annual storm sea state is within deep waters condition, while the 100 years storm is in intermediate waters.

Table 2: Extreme sea states in model and full (in brackets) scale.

Condition	H_{m0} [m]	T_p [s]	ω_p [rad/s]
Operational	0.029 (2.54)	1.18 (11.1)	5.31 (0.57)
Annual storm	0.053 (4.63)	1.36 (12.7)	4.62 (1.49)
100 years storm	0.113 (9.84)	1.568 (14.7)	4.01 (0.43)

3 NUMERICAL MODEL

In order to evaluate numerically the response of the platform, a mid fidelity approach based on linear wave theory and formulated in the frequency domain was considered. In this approach, firstly the potential hydrodynamic coefficients are computed and then additional damping and restoring coefficients are considered when solving the equation of motions, to take the viscous and mooring forces into account, respectively.

For computing the potential hydrodynamic coefficients, the Boundary Element Method is used to solve simultaneously the Bernoulli and Laplace equations, respectively:

$$p + \rho g z + \frac{1}{2}(\nabla\Phi)^2 + \rho \frac{\partial\Phi}{\partial t} = \text{constant} \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla^2\Phi = 0 \quad (2)$$

where p is the fluid pressure, ρ the fluid density, g the gravity acceleration, ϕ the fluid potential and ∇ the divergence operator.

The open source NEMOH solver was used to calculate the hydrodynamic (Kurnia & Ducrozet 2023). In this calculation, a grid of 1982 elements of half of the submerged body was created, taking advantage of the symmetry along the longitudinal plane (see Figure 5). Thus, added mass (A), potential damping (B_p) and wave excitation forces per wave height unit (F_e) were computed.

Since this formulation does not consider viscous and mooring forces, two corrections were applied to consider the main components of them: it is the pure motions viscous damping and mooring restoring forces. The mooring forces were assessed empirically. As they have an approximated linear behaviour at small amplitudes, they were assumed linear. Knowing that the damped frequencies depends on the restoring forces, the mooring restoring coefficients were found through an iterative process until reach the computed damped frequency is the same as the measured on the free decay tests. Thus, the restoring mooring matrix (C_m) was defined as:

$$C_m = \begin{bmatrix} 180.5 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 42.6 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 6.9 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (3)$$

The viscous damping forces were approximated by a linear damping force, which were characterized through free decay tests. Thus, the viscous damping matrix (B_v) was defined, only taking into account the uncoupled coefficients:

$$B_v = \begin{bmatrix} 5.34 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 12.12 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 1.23 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \end{bmatrix} \quad (4)$$

Finally, all these forces are evaluated when solving the equation of motion of the platform in the frequency domain:

$$RAO = \frac{1}{[-\omega^2(M + A) - i\omega(B_r + B_v) + (C_h + C_m)]^{-1} F_e} \quad (5)$$

where C_h is the hydrostatic restoring matrix and RAO is defined as:

$$RAO = \frac{\zeta_a}{\eta_a} \quad (6)$$

Figure 4: Experimental (at WG1) and theoretical wave energy density spectrum, (a) operational, (b) annual storm and (c) 100 years storm conditions. JONSWAP is evaluated considering experimental H_s and T_p .

Figure 5: BEM code mesh that belongs to a half of the submerged platform body, taking advantage of the longitudinal symmetry plane. Blue rows are normal vectors of each element.

where ζ_a are the motions amplitude and η_a the wave amplitude.

In order to evaluate the response of the platform in irregular waves, as the sea states assessed are within linear wave theory regime, the response spectrum of motion (S_ζ) can be calculated from the transfer function of the motions (RAO) and the wave spectrum (S_η) by:

$$S_\zeta = RAO^2 S_\eta \quad (7)$$

where S_η is the wave energy spectrum.

The mean drift forces coefficients are calculated by applying the far-field formulation (Maruo 1960, Newman 1967) implemented in NEMOH based on (Delhommeau 1987) using the Kochin function. According to this formulation, the drift force can be determined by:

$$\begin{aligned} \begin{pmatrix} F_{\text{drift},x} \\ F_{\text{drift},y} \end{pmatrix} &= c1 \begin{pmatrix} \cos \beta \\ \sin \beta \end{pmatrix} \text{Im}(\tilde{H}(\beta, \omega)) \\ &+ c2 \text{Im} \left[\int_{-\pi/2}^{\pi/2} \text{Re}(\tilde{H}(\theta, \omega)) \text{Im}(\tilde{H}^*(\theta, \omega)) \begin{pmatrix} \cos \theta \\ \sin \theta \end{pmatrix} d\theta \right] \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where

$$c1 = -2\pi\rho a\omega \quad (9)$$

$$c2 = -\frac{8\pi\rho k(k_0h)^2}{h((kh)^2 - (k_0h)^2 + k_0h)} \quad (10)$$

$F_{\text{drift},x}$ is the drift force in the x-axis, $F_{\text{drift},y}$ is the drift force in the y-axis, $\tilde{H}(\theta, \omega)$ the complex Kochin function, $\tilde{H}^*(\theta, \omega)$ the complex conjugate of Kochin function, a the wave amplitude, β the wave angle, k the wave number in finite depth, k_0 the wave number in infinite depth and h the water depth.

The complex Kochin function is calculated as a sum of radiation and diffraction components (Folley 2016), such it can be computed using the Kochin function for the diffraction potential ($\tilde{H}_D(\beta, \omega)$) and the Kochin function for the radiation potential ($\tilde{H}_R(\beta, \omega)$) obtained by NEMOH code, such that:

$$\tilde{H}(\beta, \omega) = a\tilde{H}_D(\beta, \omega)e^{i\frac{\pi}{2}} + \sum_{j=1}^6 a\tilde{X}_j(\omega)\tilde{H}_R(\beta, \omega)e^{-i\frac{\pi}{2}i\omega} \quad (11)$$

where $\tilde{X}_j(\omega)$ the motion Response Amplitude Operators (RAO)

4 RESULTS

4.1 Free decay tests

Surge, heave and pitch free decay tests were carried out. During these tests the mooring system was considered. Multiple repetitions were conducted at different initial excitation, going from 0.025 mm to 0.060 mm in surge, from -0.055 mm to -0.040 mm in heave and only -14° initial amplitude in pitch (see Figure 6). When applying the initial excitation, the other DOF were kept as close to zero as was possible and then a

full equilibrium position was generated in still water before suddenly generating the free decay. After a few periods, the reflection of the tank walls radiating into the model affected the tests, shortening the effective duration of them. Thus, only the first four peaks were considered as valid free decay in the analysis. The obtained results are summarized in Table 3, which shows the average of the multiple repetitions carried out for each motion.

Figure 6: Free decay tests of (a) surge, (b) heave and (c) pitch motions. To facilitate the analysis, $t=0$ coincide with the first positive peak, which is also the first point used in the fitting.

Table 3: Free decay tests results.

Variable	Surge	Heave	Pitch
T_d [s]	3.13	1.18	1.97
w_n [rad/s]	2.00	5.32	3.19
w_0 [rad/s]	2.01	5.33	3.20
ξ [-]	0.022	0.050	0.053

To assess the decay motions, the peak points were identified and a regression analysis using the Least Squares Method was applied in order to satisfy the $y = a \exp(bt)$ equation, where y is the motion assessed and a and b the coefficients to compute. If linear damping is assumed, b corresponds to $-\xi\omega_0$, where ξ is the damping ratio and w_0 the undamped natural frequency, which is related with the natural frequency (ω_n) by:

$$\omega_n = \omega_0 \sqrt{1 - \kappa^2} \quad (12)$$

Then, the viscous damping (B_v) is computed as:

$$B_{vi} = 2(M_i + A_i(\omega_{ni}))\omega_{0i}\xi_i - B_{pi}(\omega_{ni}) \quad (13)$$

where i denotes the assessed motion and B_p is the radiation damping computed with potential theory.

When comparing the repetitions of heave decay tests it might be noted the decayment remains almost the same for the different initial amplitudes tested. However, in the case of the surge decay tests, the decayment increases in 40% when the initial amplitude is doubled but maintaining the same oscillation frequency.

4.2 Response in regular waves

To analyse the wave and motion signals for regular wave conditions, the same procedure was applied. An integer number of periods was selected after the initial transient condition and before the reflected waves from the back wall of the tank reach the model. Then, the Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) matlab function was applied in order to identify the frequency and amplitude of the main component. In the case of wave amplitude, the amplitudes and frequencies average over the four wave gauges was evaluated of measurements without the model. Thus, experimental RAO was obtained (see Figure 8).

In order to show the influence of the corrections for mooring and viscous forces applied in the numerical approach, 3 different configuration were calculated (see Figure 8 (a), (b), (c)). First, *BEM* condition considering only the potential hydrodynamic coefficients computed by NEMOH, i.e. free floating condition in potential fluid. Second, modelling of the mooring forces through the C_m matrix was added, which is called *BEM + C_m* . And finally, the third condition *BEM + C_m + B_v* which besides modelling the mooring forces, models the viscous forces through the B_v matrix.

Figure 7: Experimental-numerical drift force comparison in regular waves.

The inclusion of mooring restoring forces through C_m matrix has an important contribution on the whole frequency domain and mainly modifying the natural frequencies. It generates a surge resonance frequency at 2 rad/s. In heave the natural frequency is

Figure 8: RAO of (a) surge, (b) heave and (c) pitch motions. In (d), (e) and (f) is showed the RAO of surge, heave and pitch motions, respectively, around the experimental frequency range. In BEM the viscous damping (B_v) and mooring restoring (C_m) coefficients matrixes are not considered, such it belongs to the free floating condition. In BEM+ C_m only C_m is evaluated and in BEM+ $C_m + B_v$ both matrixes are taken into account.

increased from 5.22 rad/s to 5.32 rad/s. Pitch natural frequency increases from 2.79 rad/s to 3.19 rad/s. Besides, this correction generated a coupling among motions, especially between surge and pitch motions, which might be noted as both natural frequencies are distinguished at each motion. Meanwhile, the viscous damping forces affects mainly the region close to the natural frequencies by reducing the motion amplitude. Then, knowing most of the wave energy is concentrated between 3 rad/s and 7 rad/s, heave and pitch motions will be the most excited because their natural frequencies are inside this range.

When comparing the numerical simulations with the experimental results (see Figure 8 (c), (d), (f)) a good agreement is observed. Although the frequency range of the experimental regular waves encompasses most sea states, it only includes the heave resonance range. The highest differences can be observed in heave RAO around the natural frequency, where the amplitudes were overestimated by the numerical model. Also, it can be observed an overestimation of pitch RAO at lowest frequencies, between 4 rad/s and 5 rad/s.

The mean drift force in x-axis is computed from the regular wave tests by assessing the sum of longitudinal component of the forces exerting by the 3 mooring lines. These results are then compared to numerical simulations obtained from Kochin functions computed by NEMOH code, see Figure 7. The comparison shows a good agreement between the numerical and experimental results, with both following the same trend. However, the numerical model tends to underestimate the magnitude of the mean drift forces,

with the discrepancies becoming more pronounced at higher frequencies.

4.3 Response in irregular waves

To assess the response of the platform in irregular waves, the measured motion and mooring tension time series signals were truncated and filtered using low pass filter. Then, the FFT matlab function was applied to these signals and the energy density spectrum were computed. In case of the numerical model, the wave energy spectrum from measurement without the model were used.

Three different approaches for evaluating the response of the platform in irregular waves are compared: one from the spectrum analysis of the experimental irregular waves time signals, and two of them using the transfer function obtained experimentally: by regular wave tests and by the numerical model (see Figure 9, Figure 10 and 11).

When comparing the experimental results, obtained with frequency and time domain approaches, a good agreement can be observed between both results. This conclusion is limited in range to the availability of experimental regular waves. The main differences can be observed in heave motion around the natural frequency where the frequency domain approach underestimate the heave response of the floating structure. This difference becomes specially larger in the operational sea state.

Overall, the results of the numerical approach demonstrate a strong correlation with the experimental data, (see Table 3). In surge motion, the response

is well simulated by the numerical model but having a difference when replicating the motions generated by surge natural frequency. It yields to differences on significant amplitude lower than 6% among all the sea states assessed. When looking at heave response, although the numerical model approximates adequately the response in annual and 100 years sea states, a larger difference can be observed on operational sea state highly concentrated around the natural frequency, such that it underestimates the response amplitude in 26%. Then, the largest differences can be found in pitch response. Although the pitch response is well simulated in operational sea state, it is underestimated in annual and 100 years storm sea states, giving large difference in significant amplitude equal to 31% and 60%, respectively.

In order to study the total mooring forces, the longitudinal component of the resulting force applied by the mooring system (F_{mx}) was defined. This variable was analysed in the same way as the motion time series by using the FFT matlab function, to obtain the energy spectrum per wave amplitude unit (S_{Fx}), see Figure 12. In these spectrum is possible to identify the influence of surge natural frequency and its harmonics. Then, in the operational sea state most of the energy is concentrated around 5.3 rad/s, which corresponds to the wave peak frequency and heave natural frequency. In the annual storm sea state, the second harmonic of surge natural frequency (4 rad/s) becomes the principal energy component. In the 100 years storm sea state the main energy component also is 4 rad/s as the wave peak frequency coincide with the second harmonic of surge natural frequency.

Table 4: Motions and mooring force statistics.

Condition	Variable	Units	Exp.	Num.	Error
Operational	x_{m0}	m	0.008	0.008	+1.5%
	z_{m0}	m	0.028	0.021	-25.6%
	θ_{m0}	°	0.53	0.54	+1.1%
Annual storm	x_{m0}	m	0.020	0.021	+5.6%
	z_{m0}	m	0.040	0.034	-13.2%
	θ_{m0}	°	1.76	2.30	+30.8%
100 years storm	x_{m0}	m	0.056	0.058	+3.0%
	z_{m0}	m	0.070	0.066	-5.8%
	θ_{m0}	°	5.2	8.3	+59.7%

5 DISCUSSION

5.1 Mooring system

The mooring system used on the physical model aimed to apply only longitudinal restoring forces. However, when there are vertical displacements of the mooring fairlead, the vertical component of the mooring lines tension generates vertical forces (F_z) and moments around Y axis (M_y), affecting the dynamic of heave and pitch motions, respectively. When looking at the results obtained in surge response, as this is the motion most influenced by mooring forces, it can

be concluded they were properly modelled with this approach as a first approximation.

The mooring system has a strong influence on the platform response, by modifying the natural frequencies and coupling the motions, being the latter clearly observed between pitch and surge in this problem. Although this approach allows to model properly the natural frequencies of high relevance on the response of the platform, it assumes the linear of mooring forces. However, since the geometrical properties of the mooring system, this assumption becomes imprecise when having large amplitudes and a combination of different motions. Thus, in order to improve the modelling of these the forces, it can be used a mooring solver by running simulations in time domain.

5.2 Viscous forces

Both in heave and pitch response, the amplitude differences between numerical and experimental results become larger when the wave peak frequency is closer to the motion natural frequency. Since the response amplitude is highly affected by viscous damping as can be observed in Figure 8, and this effects are mainly concentrated around natural frequency, the discrepancies of the numerical model results might be related to a wrong modelling of viscous forces. The main assumption followed when modelling the viscous forces in this approach were that these forces are linear and constant in all the frequency domain.

When analysing free decay tests it was obtained a good agreement by assuming it linear. However, in the surge decay tests, the decayment increases with the initial amplitude of the tests. In the case of heave motion, does not seem to be a significant relation between the initial amplitude and the damping ratio in the range tested. Whereas, as in pitch motion only one decay test was performed, it is not possible to make conclusions in this matter. The amplitude dependence of the damping forces observed in surge motion reflects the complexity of viscous forces. Other example of the influence of viscous effects on the platform response is can be clearly noted when looking at the difference between both experimental results obtained in operational sea state, as the only difference between both results are the wave amplitudes. These phenomenons could be associated to vortex shedding as has been assessed on damping plates research, where added mass and viscous damping coefficients depend on frequency and amplitude of the oscillatory motion (Rusch et al. 2020, Lopez-Pavon & Souto-Iglesias 2015).

The motion amplitude dependence of radiation forces can not be modelled through the numerical model proposed in the current work, as it assumes this coefficient depends on the frequency only. In the free decay tests the frequency of the oscillation remains the same, being this the natural frequency, while the amplitude decays. In order to better assess the ef-

Figure 9: (a) surge, (b) heave and (c) pitch response spectrum in operational sea state. Exp. FFT corresponds to the spectral analysis of the irregular waves time signals, $S_\eta \cdot RAO_{BEM}^2$ to the frequency domain approach using numerical RAO and $S_\eta \cdot RAO_{exp}^2$ to the frequency domain approach using the experimental RAO.

Figure 10: (a) surge, (b) heave and (c) pitch response spectrum in annual storm sea state. Exp. FFT corresponds to the spectral analysis of the irregular waves time signals, $S_\eta \cdot RAO_{BEM}^2$ to the frequency domain approach using numerical RAO and $S_\eta \cdot RAO_{exp}^2$ to the frequency domain approach using the experimental RAO.

Figure 11: (a) surge, (b) heave and (c) pitch response spectrum in 100 years storm sea state. Exp. FFT corresponds to the spectral analysis of the irregular waves time signals, $S_\eta \cdot RAO_{BEM}^2$ to the frequency domain approach using numerical RAO and $S_\eta \cdot RAO_{exp}^2$ to the frequency domain approach using the experimental RAO.

fect of frequency and amplitude of motions in damping coefficient, forced oscillations tests can be done. Through these tests is possible to obtain the added mass at the same time than viscous damping.

The uncoupled damping coefficients, which were measured in this study, are the most relevant in the dynamic of the platform. However, due to there is a strong coupling between pitch and surge motions in the dynamic of the platform, would be relevant to model these forces also in order to achieve a better accuracy of the numerical model.

5.3 Numerical method scope

The main advantage of the numerical model in the present work is the low use of resources, such a calculation could take a couple of hours on a mid-range computer. However, its accuracy is not enough to perform a complete hydrodynamic analysis when motions becomes large as in extreme conditions or when the wave frequency coincide with the resonance frequency of motions since nonlinear effects becomes relevant. Besides, it needs the input of moor-

Figure 12: Longitudinal mooring force energy spectrum.

ing and viscous forces. While the mooring forces can be assessed empirically or analytically with an acceptable precision, viscous forces can not be assessed in the same way. In the present work, part of these forces were assessed experimentally through free decay tests. Nevertheless, these experiments are resource consuming such is necessary to fabricate a model and its mooring system. Then, a smart system has to be design to make decay tests in pure motions.

Alternative ways to characterize viscous forces can be considered. One of them is using an actuator system to make forced oscillation tests, as was discussed in the previous section. However, the latter option further increasing the resources needed. Other option is to perform numerical simulations which be able to model the viscous effects with high accuracy such as CFD. By running free decay or forced oscillation simulations, should not be needed consider wave generation methods. Besides, they have a short duration and can use a reduced domain if numerical absorption boundaries are used. These aspects means considerable computing time saving. The critical aspect of these numerical simulations would be the mooring system modelling as, depending on the mooring type and numerical model used, might be necessary to couple a mooring solver for running free decay tests.

6 CONCLUSIONS

The response of a generic semi-submersible FOWT in operational and extreme conditions based on a Chilean location was assessed experimentally and numerically at 1:87.2 scale. Surge, heave and pitch motions as well as mooring loads were analysed, obtaining the significant amplitudes in each condition by carrying out spectral analysis.

Free decay tests were carried out to study the natural frequency for each DOF and the total damping at this frequency. Also, restoring forces exerted by the mooring system were linearized by using the results of these tests, deriving the uncoupled components. These viscous and mooring forces approximation was used as input in a numerical model based

on the Boundary Element Method and potential theory. A strong correlation between numerical simulations and experimental results was obtained, having the largest differences in pitch and heave response when wave peak frequency coincide with the motions resonance region.

Considering the good approximation of mooring system and that all sea states accomplish with linear wave theory, the differences of the numerical results are mainly related to viscous effects. Thus, added mass and damping coefficients need to be assessed deeply in order to improve the accuracy of this method, which could be done experimentally or using CFD solvers.

Additionally, the response of the platform in the same sea states was assessed experimentally through the transfer function of the motions (RAO) measured in regular wave tests. A good agreement between both experimental results was obtained in the frequency range considered, having the largest differences in heave motion close to natural frequency. However, the tested regular waves do not cover the pitch and surge natural frequencies, being not possible to assess the accuracy of this approach in deep. Also, drift force is analysed from regular wave tests and compared with numerical simulations by using Kochin function, obtaining a good agreement between numerical and experimental results.

The main discrepancies in the numerical model results are concentrated around the motion natural frequencies, highlighting the need for better modeling of viscous forces. To address this aspect, forced oscillation tests can be conducted both numerically and experimentally. Additionally, to enhance the accuracy of the mooring system simulation, time domain approaches might be considered, allowing for the coupling of mooring solvers.

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